

FRACTURE AND DAMAGE OF CARBON NANOTUBE MODIFIED HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with an approach to strengthen endless carbon fibre reinforced composites in their interlaminar direction by the addition of nanoparticles into the matrix phase, namely by means of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). The manufacturing of the hybrid composites was performed by the industrially relevant process of vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding. The MWCNTs used are endowed with a proper surface functionalization in order to improve the dispersion quality and stability, as well as to lower the viscosity of the nanoparticle modified resin system, facilitating the injection process. Fracture mechanical analysis of carbon fibre test laminates with up to 1 wt.% MWCNTs in the matrix phase exhibited an increase in interlaminar Mode I fracture toughness in the regimes of crack-onset (~17 %) and propagation (~10 %), as determined by crack resistance curves. Mode II fracture behaviour remained unaffected. In terms of impact response, the hybrid composites exhibit a more elastic response leading to a decrease in dissipated energy throughout the impact experiment. The modification with MWCNTs retards the onset of delamination, the peak force is elevated and the load drop in the case of fibre breakage is diminished, i.e. the damage resistance is enhanced. Ultrasonic investigations after impact revealed the reduced size of damaged areas. Ultimately, the residual compressive strength of the hybrid composites is enhanced.

1 INTRODUCTION

Impact-induced damage in fibre reinforced composite structures is limiting their applications. While high energy impact loads lead to complete puncture, low energy impact results in micro-cracks and delaminations between the inner plies of the composite and the damage is barely visible on the surface. The consequence is a loss in mechanical performance, including in-plane stiffness and strength and unperceived crack and delamination growth in service leads to catastrophic failure [1]–[3]. Throughout impact, complex failure mechanisms take place in fibre reinforced laminate structures. The involved energy absorbing mechanisms are shear-induced Mode II delaminations and matrix cracking, fibre breakage and kinking of filaments [4].

The reported increases in Mode II delamination resistance of multi-scale composites built-up of endless carbon fibres and additionally reinforced with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are an encouraging attempt toward damage optimisation of laminated structures, since the correlation between shear-induced delamination and damage resistance is well known [1]–[3], [5]–[7]. Ashrafi et al. [8] modified carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRPs) prepared by prepreg-technology with single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) and the damage behaviour remained practically unaffected. Kostopoulos et al. [9] modified CFRPs (Prepreg) with multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and observed a more pronounced increase in residual compression strength after impact (CAI) at higher impact loadings. The contributing failure mechanisms of the CNTs were identified as CNT-pullout and CNT-fracture. Siegfried et al. [10] prepared CFRPs with MWCNT addition by resin transfer moulding

(RTM) and noticed a moderate loss in damage resistance (increase in delamination areas), while CAI remained unaffected.

In this study, we prepared CFRP laminates modified with 0.5 and 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs by RTM technology and assessed the interlaminar fracture toughness and the damage behaviour by low-velocity impact testing. The MWCNTs used are surface treated by initial oxidation and subsequent epoxy functionalization, enhancing the filler-matrix compatibility and interfacial (shear) strength. The effect of MWCNT addition on the damage response of the hybrid composites is assessed by determination of force – and energy – time courses during impact. We observed an increase of elasticity respectively stiffness, resulting in an enhancement of damage resistance while impact loading.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Surface treatment and dispersion of carbon nanotubes

Surface-modified MWCNTs of type Baytubes® C150P (Bayer MaterialScience AG, Leverkusen, Germany), dispersed in the tetra-functional epoxy resin tetraglycidylmethylenedianiline (TGMDA, Epikote™ Resin 496, epoxy equivalent weight of ~115 g/eq., Momentive Specialty Chemicals Inc., Waterford, NY, USA) were provided as a masterbatch (Bayer MaterialScience AG). The surface modification – conducted by the supplier – was done by initial oxidation in acetic conditions and subsequent functionalization with diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, Dow® Liquid Epoxy Resin D.E.R.™ 331™), epoxy equivalent weight of 187 ± 5 g/eq), analogous as described by [11]. The dispersion of the surface-functionalized MWCNTs was performed by 3-roll-milling (EXAKT Advanced Technologies GmbH, Norderstedt, Germany).

2.2 Resin formulation and vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding of test laminates

The as-received masterbatch was diluted with TGMDA to the desired concentration, thoroughly stirred for 30 min in an oil bath at 80 °C and the amine hardener 4,4'-Methylenbis(2,6-diisopropylanilin) (MDIPA, EPIKURE™ Curing Agent 385, amine equivalent weight ~92 g/eq, Momentive Specialty Inc.) was added in stoichiometric amount.

Carbon fibre-reinforced test laminates with and without MWCNT addition to the epoxy matrix were produced using vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding (RTM). The aluminium mould with a cavity of approximately 40 cm x 40 cm was preconditioned with release agent (Loctite 770-NC) and thoroughly dried before placing the carbon fibres. Twelve, respectively 16 plies of a bidirectional non crimp stitch-bonded carbon fibre fabric (Tenax®-E HTS40 F13 12k, 800 tex, Toho Tenax Europe GmbH, Wuppertal, Germany) with a fibre areal weight of 268 g/m^2 (Saertex GmbH & Co. KG, Saerbeck, Germany) were placed in the mould equipped with 3.3 mm (for $[(0/90)_5 (90/0)_1]_s$ layup), respectively 4.4 mm (for $[(\pm 45) (0/90)]_{4s}$ layup) thick frames, leading to composites with fibre volume contents of approximately 55 %. The closed mould was put into a hot press (LZT 110 L, Maschinenfabrik Langzauner GmbH, Lambrecht, Austria), evacuated, and heated to 140 °C. The fabrics were impregnated with the epoxy systems with and without MWCNT modification applying a pressure of 0.2 MPa. After complete impregnation, a dwell pressure of 0.5 MPa was applied for 5 min. The press was heated to 180 °C and curing proceeded for 2 h.

2.3 Mechanical characterization

Determination of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} was done referring to ISO 15024 using at least 5 double cantilever beam (DCB) test specimens with aluminium end blocks. A PTFE film insert with a thickness of 13 µm and length of approx. 60 mm was laminated in the mid plane and served as initial crack. The initial crack length a_0 was 50 mm, no precracking was performed and crack propagation was observed using a magnifying glass. White painting and increment marks every 2.5 mm for the first 5 mm and then every 5 mm up to 50 mm assisted for visual crack tip

identification. Testing was performed on a universal testing machine Zwick Z2.5 (Zwick GmbH, Ulm, Germany) at constant cross-head speed of 5 mm/min. The loads P and the corresponding displacements δ were recorded for the crack length a .

Corrected beam theory was used for the calculation of the critical strain energy release rate using the expression:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a+|\Delta|)} \times \frac{F}{N} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where F is the large-displacement correction, N the load block correction and Δ is the x-intercept of the linear fit obtained by the relation between the delamination length a and the compliance C , established by plotting the cube root of the compliance divided by the end block correction $N [(C/N)^{1/3}]$ as a function of the delamination length a . All results were used to plot a delamination resistance curve (R-curve).

Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IIc} was evaluated following DIN 65563 using at least five end-notched flexure (ENF) test specimens placed in a three-point bending setup. The span length was set to 100 mm, the radii of the supporting rolls were 5 mm, the radius of the bending die was 12.5 mm and the initial precrack length a of the ENF test specimens was 20 mm. Critical energy release rate in mode II under plain strain conditions was determined using the expression

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9F^2Ca^2}{2W(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where F is the force at crack growth initiation, C is the compliance of the test specimen, W its width, and L is the distance between the bending die and the supporting rolls. As a conservative estimation of the compliance, the unmodified beam theory is usually adequate and was calculated using

$$C = \frac{2L^3 + 3a^3}{8E\delta d^3} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where E is the bending modulus in axial direction, δ is the deflection, and d is the beam half height.

Impact testing and determination of compression strength after impact (CAI) was performed according to Airbus Test Method AITM 1-0010. For impact testing a falling impact tester (CEAST Fractovis Plus, Compagnia Europea Apparecchi Scientifici, Torino, Italy) equipped with an instrumented steel impactor of diameter 16 mm, hemisphere radius of 8 mm attached to an aluminium frame with a total weight of 2.008 kg. Rectangular shape carbon fibre reinforced test specimens with quasi-isotropic lay-up $[(\pm 45)(0/90)]_{4s}$, length of 150 mm and width of 100 mm were subjected to impact testing at an energy level of 30 J. Delamination was determined as described below.

The compression testing was carried out on the impacted specimens using a universal testing machine Zwick 1485 (Zwick GmbH, Ulm, Germany) at constant cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. Impacted test specimens were mounted in a compression after impact test tool as described in AITM 1-0010.

2.4 Non-destructive evaluation

Quality inspection and non-destructive determination of damaged areas after impact testing was performed using ultrasonic inspection (C-scan, USPC 3010 VHF, impuls-echo, Ultraschall-Prüftechnik Dr. Hillger, Braunschweig, Germany). Determination of delaminated areas was conducted using the built-in software option for determination of damaged areas applying to the C-scan obtained by evaluating the back wall echo.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation and the discussion of the results are divided into the sections of interlaminar fracture toughness and damage. Within the part of fracture toughness, the results of the interlaminar and nanocomposites fracture toughness testing are presented. The damage section describes the impact responses by depiction of the force – time and energy – time evolution during impact testing and the role of the MWCNT addition into the CFRP matrix is evaluated by the determination of indentation depth, dissipated energy, delamination area and residual compression strength.

3.1 Interlaminar fracture toughness

Determination of interlaminar fracture toughness by means of crack resistance curves (R-curves) is presented in Figure 1 by plots of interlaminar energy release rate in Mode I G_{Ic} vs. crack propagation length Δa for the CFRP reference system based on TGMDA and the hybrid composites. The addition with 0.5 and 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs in the matrix phase leads to an increase in $G_{Ic, onset}$ ($\Delta a \sim 0$) as well as in the region of (stable) crack propagation. The comparison of the discrete values of $G_{Ic, onset}$ and averaged energy release rate $G_{Ic, mean}$ presented in Table 1 reveals more pronounced gains in the onset values of G_{Ic} of ~10 and ~17 % for the hybrid composites containing 0.5 and 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs respectively. The crack initiation behaviour of the CFRPs is mainly affected by its matrix toughness. The comparison with the matrix respectively nanocomposites fracture toughness demonstrates, that the increase in (MWCNT nanocomposites) fracture toughness accounts for the observed $G_{Ic, onset}$ behaviour of the hybrid composites. In the region of crack propagation, the effect of matrix toughness is superimposed by the phenomenon of large scale fibre-bridging [12], [13].

Determination of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness revealed no pronounced influence of the MWCNTs, since the observed rise in G_{IIc} in the case of the 0.5 wt.-% MWCNTs hybrid composite is believed to be originated in the lower fibre volume content of the test laminate, see Table 1.

Figure 1: Interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} crack resistance curve of the CFRP reference system based on TGMDA and the carbon fiber hybrid systems containing 0.5 wt.-% respectively 1.0 wt.-% surface functionalized MWCNTs in the matrix phase. An increase in the onset as well in the propagation values of G_{Ic} is apparent through the addition of the CNTs.

Value	Unit	Thermoset & CFRP reference	0.5 wt.-% MWCNTs	1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs
K_{Ic}	$\text{MPa m}^{0.5}$	0.61 ± 0.06	0.68 ± 0.03 (+11 %)	0.73 ± 0.02 (+19 %)
$G_{Ic, \text{onset}(5\% \text{ max})}$	$[\text{J/m}^2]$	246 ± 9	271 ± 19 (+10 %)	288 ± 27 (+17 %)
$G_{Ic, \text{mean}}$	$[\text{J/m}^2]$	391 ± 15	423 ± 30 (+8 %)	429 ± 13 (+10 %)
G_{IIc}	$[\text{J/m}^2]$	1046 ± 125	$1223 \pm 112^*$	1079 ± 129

* slightly elevated laminate thickness, i.e. reduced fibre volume content yields increased G_{IIc}

Table 1: Mechanical values of thermoset & CFRP reference system and nano- & hybrid composites containing MWCNT additivation.

3.2 Damage

The force – time and energy – time evolutions during 30 J impacts are depicted in Figure 2 for the CFRP reference system and the hybrid composites containing 0.5 wt.-% and 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs in the matrix phase. The onset of delamination, apparent from the first marked load drop in the force – time course after approximately 0.3 ms, is associated to matrix cracks and setting in of delamination [3], [14]–[16]. The additivation with MWCNTs retards the damage initiation in the hybrid composites, emerging after reaching slightly higher loads. The load furtherly increases until reaching a maximum (~12 kN) and is followed by a sudden reduction, caused by a loss of elasticity of the test samples originated in fibre breakage. The amount of fibre damage correlates with the decrease in load and is reduced through the MWCNT additivation in the hybrid composites.

Figure 2: Force – & energy – time evolution during 30 J impacts in the CFRP reference system and hybrid composites containing 0.5 and 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs in the matrix. The addition of CNTs leads to a delayed onset of delamination (force drop after ~5 kN at ~0.3 ms) and a reduction in fiber breakage (apparent from the reduction in sudden load drop after reaching its maximum at ~1.0 ms). The proportion of dissipated energy is reduced, i.e. the hybrid composites impact response is more elastic.

Figure 3: Role of MWCNTs on the damage behavior of CFRP hybrid systems. The addition leads to a reduction of indentation depth d_{dent} and dissipated energy E_{diss} during impact, lowering the delaminated area A_{del} and resulting in increased residual compression strength after impact CAI.

The maxima of the energy – time courses depict the impact energy introduced into the material and are set to 30 J. The absolute values of the succeeding declines in energy are attributed to elastically stored energy portions being bounced back. The energy parts remaining present after the impact event (after ~3.0 ms) are designated to the dissipation (energy devoted to plastic deformation and fracture). The modification of the CFRP matrix with surface functionalized MWCNTs raises the elastic energy part, respectively diminishes the energy dissipation for up to ~20 % ($E_{diss} = 14$ J in the case of the CFRP reference system and $E_{diss} = 11$ J in the case of the hybrid composite containing 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs), and is – in that extent – not yet reported in literature [8]–[10], [17].

An overview of observed maximum indentation depth of the impactor d_{dent} , energy dissipation E_{diss} , delaminated area A_{del} as determined by ultrasonic inspection of the samples after the impact event and the residual compression strength CAI is depicted in Figure 3 for the CFRP reference system and the hybrid composites containing 0.5 and 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs. Beside the aforementioned reduction in energy dissipation during impact, the more elastic behavior of the hybrid composites results in inferior indentation depths of the impactor. The decrement in delaminated areas (~37 % for 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs) designates the increase in the damage resistance of the MWCNT reinforced hybrid CFRPs. Ultimately, an increment in residual compression strength from ~205 MPa to ~225 MPa evolves from the matrix modification with 1.0 wt.-% MWCNTs in the matrix phase of the hybrid composite.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The damage behaviour of CFRPs produced by VARTM is enhanced through the addition of surface functionalized MWCNTs into the matrix phase. Although the influence of the nanotubes on the interlaminar fracture toughness in Mode II is negligible, an augmentation in damage resistance is observed for the hybrid composites. The nanotubes improve the matrix' fracture toughness and sensitivity toward crack initiation, thus the onset of delamination during impact is retarded. The elasticity of the hybrid composites is raised, thus less impact energy is dissipated and the extent of fibre breakage is reduced. This enhancement of damage resistance leads to an increment in residual compression strength of the MWCNT additivated hybrid CFRPs.

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